

Study of Foeto-Maternal Outcome in Pregnancies with First-Trimester Bleeding PervaginaMampi Khatun¹, Swaralipi Misra², Jayeeta Mukherjee³, Sougata Kumar Burman⁴¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics &Gynaecology, COM & JNM Hospital, The West Bengal University of Health Sciences, Kalyani, Nadia- 741235, West Bengal, India²RMO cum CT, Department of Obstetrics &Gynaecology, COM & JNM Hospital, The West Bengal University of Health Sciences, Kalyani, Nadia- 741235, West Bengal, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics &Gynaecology, COM & JNM Hospital, The West Bengal University of Health Sciences, Kalyani , Nadia- 741235, West Bengal, India⁴Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, College of Medicine and JNM Hospital, The West Bengal University of Health Sciences, Kalyani, Nadia- 741235, West Bengal

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Introduction:** First-trimester vaginal bleeding is a common obstetric complication occurring in approximately 20-25% of pregnancies and is a significant cause of concern for patients and clinicians alike. The etiology of bleeding in early pregnancy varies widely, ranging from benign causes such as implantation bleeding to more serious conditions like threatened miscarriage, ectopic pregnancy, and molar pregnancy.**Aims and Objectives:** To evaluate the foeto-maternal outcomes in pregnancies with first-trimester vaginal bleeding and to assess its association with adverse pregnancy, neonatal, and maternal complications.**Materials and Methods:** The present study was a Prospective study. This Study was conducted from December2020 to July2021 at Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, NilratanSircar Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata. Total 60 patients were included in this study.**Result:** In our study, 88.09% of cases with abnormal ultrasound and 100% with an open cervical os resulted in abortion, while mode of delivery showed no significant association with gestational age (p=0.918). Among 21 live-born neonates, 28.57% had IUGR and 23.81% had respiratory distress, with 45% requiring NICU admission. Maternal complications included PIH in 30% and PPRM in 15% of cases.**Conclusion:** In our study, first-trimester bleeding was associated with a wide spectrum of maternal and neonatal outcomes. Vaginal delivery was the predominant mode of birth, and women without a prior history of abortion generally had more favorable pregnancy courses.**Keywords:** Bleeding, Pregnancy, Outcome, Abortion.

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Introduction

First-trimester vaginal bleeding is a common obstetric complication occurring in approximately 20-25% of pregnancies and is a significant cause of concern for patients and clinicians alike. The etiology of bleeding in early pregnancy varies widely, ranging from benign causes such as implantation bleeding to more serious conditions like threatened miscarriage, ectopic pregnancy, and molar pregnancy [1,2].

This complication has been linked to increased risks of adverse pregnancy outcomes, including miscarriage, preterm labor, low birth weight, and perinatal mortality [3]. Several studies have demonstrated that first-trimester bleeding may also be associated with placental abnormalities such as placenta previa and abruption, as well as fetal

growth restriction [4, 5]. Early identification and appropriate monitoring are essential to improve foeto-maternal outcomes in these pregnancies. Despite advancements in diagnostic and therapeutic strategies, there remains a lack of comprehensive data, especially from resource-limited settings, regarding the factors influencing prognosis in pregnancies complicated by first-trimester bleeding. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the foeto-maternal outcomes associated with first-trimester bleeding per vagina, providing insight for better clinical management and counseling.

Materials and Methods**Study Type:** Prospective study**Study Design:** Longitudinal Study

Place of Study: Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Nilratan Sircar Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata.

Period of Study-December 2020 to July 2021

Study Population: Consenting Patients presenting with first trimester bleeding per vagina in OPD, emergency and indoor in the Department Of Obstetrics and Gynecology within the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Women with months of amenorrhea of <3 months.
2. Women with positive pregnancy test.
3. Women with bleeding pervagina in first trimester of pregnancy.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Women with chronic medical complications including diabetes and hypertension.
2. Women with a history of infertility.
3. Women with bad obstetric history (h/o >3 first trimester abortion in previous pregnancy).
4. Women with history of bleeding diathesis.
5. All patient with more than 12 completed weeks of gestation.
6. Multiple gestations.
7. Molar pregnancy.

Sample Size: So we take 60 as minimal sample size for the study.

Study Variables

- Age
- Parity
- Socioeconomic status
- Period of gestation
- History of previous abortion.
- Presentation
- Duration of bleeding
- Type of bleeding
- Ultrasonography examination
- Blood examination
- General examination and Obstetrical examination

Statistical Analysis: For statistical analysis, data were initially entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and then analyzed using SPSS (version 27.0; SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) and GraphPad Prism (version 5). Numerical variables were summarized using means and standard deviations, while Data were entered into Excel and analyzed using SPSS and GraphPad Prism. Numerical variables were summarized using means and standard deviations, while categorical variables were described with counts and percentages. Two-sample t-tests were used to compare independent groups, while paired t-tests accounted for correlations in paired data. Chi-square tests (including Fisher's exact test for small sample sizes) were used for categorical data comparisons. P-values ≤ 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Result

Table 1: Distribution of Pelvic Examination Findings, Mode of Delivery, and Previous Abortion History among Study Participants

		N	%
PV Examination	OS open	29	48.33
	OS closed	30	50
	Not done	1	1.67
	Total	60	100
Mode of Delivery	Vaginal delivery	15	71.43
	LSCS	6	28.57
	Total	21	100
Previous abortion	A0	41	68.33
	A1	13	21.67
	A2	6	10
	Total	60	100

Table 2: Association of Clinical and Ultrasound Findings with Pregnancy Outcomes in Women with First-Trimester Bleeding

Outcome		N	%	P-value
Vaginal delivery	Delivery at term	5	33.33	0.918
	Delivery at preterm	10	66.67	
	Total	15	100	
LSCS	Delivery at term	2	33.33	0.918
	Delivery at preterm	4	66.67	
	Total	6	100	
USG within normal limit	Abortion	0	0	<0.001

	Laparotomy	0	0	
	Delivery at term	7	38.89	
	Delivery at preterm	11	61.11	
	Total	18	100	
USG abnormal	Abortion	37	88.09	
	Laparotomy	2	4.76	
	Delivery at term	0	0	
	Delivery at preterm	3	7.14	
	Total	42	100	
OS open	Abortion	29	100	<0.001
	Laparotomy	0	0	
	Delivery at term	0	0	
	Delivery at preterm	0	0	
	Total	29	100	
OS closed	Abortion	8	26.67	
	Laparotomy	2	6.67	
	Delivery at term	7	23.33	
	Delivery at preterm	13	43.33	
	Total	30	100	
Not done	Abortion	0	0	
	Laparotomy	0	0	
	Delivery at term	0	0	
	Delivery at preterm	1	100	
	Total	1	100	
Past history of abortion (Spontaneous abortion and MTP)	Abortion	14	82.35	0.005
	Laparotomy	2	11.76	
	Delivery at term	0	0	
	Delivery at preterm	1	5.88	
	Total	17	100	
Past history of vaginal delivery	Abortion	2	28.57	
	Laparotomy	0	0	
	Delivery at term	2	28.57	
	Delivery at preterm	3	42.85	
	Total	7	100	
Past history of LSCS	Abortion	2	33.3	
	Laparotomy	0	0	
	Delivery at term	0	0	
	Delivery at preterm	4	66.7	
	Total	6	100	

Table 3: Distribution of cases according to neonatal complications

Neonatal complications	N	%
IUGR	6	28.57%
Jaundice	1	4.76
MAS	1	4.76
RDS	5	23.81
Nil	8	38.09
Total	21	100

Table 4: Distribution of cases according to NICU admission of babies

NICU admission	N	%
Yes	10	45
No	11	55
Total	21	100

Table 5: Showing maternal outcomes

Maternal outcomes	N	%
Severe Anaemia	1	5
PIH	5	30
Placenta previa	2	10
Placental abruption	1	5
PPH	1	5
PPROM	3	15
No complication	8	30
Total	21	100

Figure 1: Distribution of cases according to NICU admission of babies

Figure 2: Showing maternal outcomes

In our study, per vaginal examination revealed that the majority of patients had a closed cervical os (50%), followed closely by an open os in 48.33% of cases, while in 1.67% the examination was not performed. Among the 21 women who delivered, vaginal delivery was the most common mode (71.43%), with lower segment caesarean section (LSCS) accounting for 28.57% of deliveries. Regarding previous obstetric history, 68.33% of women had no history of abortion, whereas 21.67% had one abortion and 10% had two previous abortions.

In our study, the mode of delivery did not show a statistically significant association with gestational

age at delivery ($p=0.918$), with both vaginal delivery and LSCS groups having a higher proportion of preterm deliveries (66.67% each) compared to term deliveries (33.33%).

Ultrasound findings were strongly associated with pregnancy outcomes ($p<0.001$), as all cases with normal scans resulted in live births (38.89% at term and 61.11% preterm), whereas abnormal scans were predominantly associated with abortions (88.09%) and a small proportion required laparotomy (4.76%). Cervical os status on per vaginal examination also showed a significant association with outcome ($p<0.001$); all women with an open os experienced abortion, while those

with a closed os had varied outcomes, including abortion (26.67%), laparotomy (6.67%), term delivery (23.33%), and preterm delivery (43.33%). Past history of abortion was significantly related to adverse outcomes ($p=0.005$), with the majority (82.35%) resulting in abortion during the current pregnancy. In contrast, women with a history of vaginal delivery or LSCS showed higher proportions of preterm delivery (42.85% and 66.7%, respectively) compared to term deliveries.

In our study, among the 21 live-born neonates, the most common complication was intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) observed in 28.57% of cases, followed by respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) in 23.81%. Jaundice and meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS) were noted in 4.76% each, while 38.09% of neonates had no complications.

In our study, out of 21 live-born neonates, 45% required NICU admission, while 55% did not require any intensive care support.

In our study, among the 21 women who delivered, the most common maternal complication was pregnancy-induced hypertension (PIH) in 30% of cases, followed by preterm premature rupture of membranes (PPROM) in 15% and placenta previa in 10%. Severe anaemia, placental abruption, and postpartum haemorrhage (PPH) were each observed in 5% of cases, while 30% of women had no maternal complications.

Discussion

In our study, ultrasound findings and cervical os status were the most significant predictors of pregnancy outcome, with abnormal scans and an open os being strongly associated with abortion, while normal scans more frequently resulted in live births. Similar results were reported by De Vilbiss et al. (2020) [6], who demonstrated that transvaginal ultrasound indicators such as fetal cardiac activity and subchorionic hematoma size have high prognostic value in first-trimester bleeding.

We found that all women with an open os aborted, consistent with Amirkhani et al. (2013) [7], who reported high rates of pregnancy loss in similar cases. Past history of abortion in our cohort was associated with a significantly higher risk of adverse outcome, suggesting that recurrent early loss may reflect persistent risk factors such as uterine anomalies or placental insufficiency. Our study also found high rates of preterm delivery in both vaginal and LSCS groups. Neonatal complications in our series, notably IUGR and respiratory distress syndrome. Collectively, our findings support the conclusion that first-trimester bleeding, particularly when accompanied by abnormal ultrasound or an open cervical os,

warrants vigilant antenatal surveillance to optimize both maternal and neonatal outcomes.

Conclusion

In our study, first-trimester bleeding was associated with a wide spectrum of maternal and neonatal outcomes. Vaginal delivery was the predominant mode of birth, and women without a prior history of abortion generally had more favorable pregnancy courses. Adverse outcomes were strongly linked to abnormal ultrasound findings and an open cervical os on per vaginal examination, while a closed os was associated with more varied results. Neonatal complications included growth restriction and respiratory distress, with some requiring intensive care admission. On the maternal side, hypertensive disorders, premature rupture of membranes, and placental abnormalities were notable complications, although a proportion of women experienced no adverse events. Overall, the findings underscore the importance of early evaluation and close antenatal monitoring in pregnancies complicated by first-trimester bleeding to optimize maternal and neonatal health.

Reference

1. Amirkhani Z, Akhlaghdoust M, Abedian M, Salehi GR, Zarbati N, Mogharehabet M, Arefian S, Jafarabadi M. Maternal and perinatal outcomes in pregnant women with first trimester vaginal bleeding. *Journal of family & reproductive health*. 2013 Jun;7(2):57.
2. Yakistiran B, Yuce T, Soylemez F. First trimester bleeding and pregnancy outcomes: case-control study. *International Journal of Womens Health and Reproduction Sciences*. 2016;4(1).
3. Günay T, Yardımcı OD. How does subchorionic hematoma in the first trimester affect pregnancy outcomes? *Archives of Medical Science: AMS*. 2021 Jan 8;18(3):639.
4. Shaamash AH, Aly HA, Abdel-Aleem M, Akhnowkh SN. Clinical and ultrasound evaluation of early threatened miscarriage to predict pregnancy continuation up to 28 weeks: a prospective cohort study. *Journal of ultrasound in medicine*. 2020 Sep;39(9):1777-85.
5. Sammut L, Bezzina P, Gibbs V, Agius JC. Assessing the predictive value of first trimester ultrasound and biochemical markers in miscarriage: a scoping review. *Radiography*. 2024 Aug 1;30(5):1368-75.
6. DeVilbiss EA, Mumford SL, Sjaarda LA, Connell MT, Plowden TC, Andriessen VC, Perkins NJ, Hill MJ, Silver RM, Schisterman EF. Prediction of pregnancy loss by early first trimester ultrasound characteristics. *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology*. 2020

- Aug 1;223(2):242-e1.
7. Amirkhani Z, Akhlaghdoust M, Abedian M, Salehi GR, Zarbati N, Mogharehabed M, Arefian S, Jafarabadi M. Maternal and perinatal outcomes in pregnant women with first trimester vaginal bleeding. *Journal of family & reproductive health*. 2013 Jun; 7(2):57.